

Supplemental figure 1

Supplemental figure 2

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 1.

Twice-daily lauric acid-treated mice show higher *Selenop* gene expression and lower phospho-Akt levels.

A: body weight, B: food intake, C: blood glucose and insulin levels during glucose tolerance test, D: blood glucose during insulin tolerance test, E: blood glucose during pyruvate tolerance test, F and G: hepatic gene expression levels, H: serum triglyceride, I: serum fatty acid, J: HbA1c, K: hepatic gene expression levels. Data represent mean \pm S.E. (error bars). (n = 5. One extreme outlier was excluded from the vehicle group). Mice have injected intraperitoneally 10 mU/bodyweight of insulin after 12 hours of fasting. After 15 minutes of insulin injection, mice were euthanized to isolate tissue samples. *, p < 0.05; **, p < 0.01; ***, p < 0.001 versus vehicle-treated mice. N. S., not significant.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 2.

Insulin signaling in the liver, skeletal muscle, and eWAT of twice-daily lauric acid-treated mice.

A: Protein levels and B-H: quantitative determination of the liver, skeletal muscle, and eWAT (n = 5. One extreme outlier was excluded from vehicle group). Mice have injected intraperitoneally 10 mU/bodyweight of insulin after 12 hours of fasting. After 15 minutes of insulin injection, mice were euthanized to isolate tissue samples. *, p < 0.05; **, p < 0.01; ***, p < 0.001 versus vehicle-treated mice. N. S., not significant.